

Deliverable D1.2:

QC/QA procedures for atmospheric radon measurements

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Project executive summary

Radon is a unique atmospheric tracer. High-quality direct and indirect measurements of radon concentration can advance climate and atmospheric sciences, radiation protection and nuclear surveillance. These observations will reduce uncertainty in baseline characterisation of European greenhouse gas (GHG) levels and assist in environmental studies. The EU-funded NuClim project aims to investigate the influence of terrestrial factors on air masses, measure pollution events and explore the impact of natural planktonic communities on GHG emissions. Additionally, it will analyse marine boundary layer clouds and aerosols, and study wet deposition and meteorological processes affecting ambient gamma dose rates for nuclear surveillance networks.

Deliverable executive summary

This deliverable summarises observations collected as part of the NuClim campaign at the Eastern North Atlantic ENA-ARM station in Graciosa Island that pertain to atmospheric radon measurements. The document outlines the quality-control procedures routinely applied to the measurements, as well as the quality-assurance procedures, including calibration and estimation of instrumental background, that ensure the data provided by NuClim are reliable and suitable for use both within the project consortium and by external users.

Glossary

ANSTO	Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation, Australia
ARM	Atmospheric Radiation Measurement
ENA	Eastern North Atlantic
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
INESC TEC	Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science, Portugal
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	7
2. Atmospheric radon measurements.....	7
3. Data preprocessing.....	8
4. Data quality control.....	9
Time series plots.....	9
Quality control of background and calibration measurements.....	9
Quality control of normal measurements.....	11
5. Data quality assurance.....	13
Calibration.....	13
Instrumental background.....	14
Calculation of radon concentration.....	15
References.....	16
Appendix – Jupyter notebook.....	17

1. Introduction

In July 2025 an ANSTO 1500 L two-filter dual-flow-loop radon monitor was installed on Graciosa Island, at the Eastern North Atlantic (ENA) station of the Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) program, as described in NuClim’s D1.1 on the field campaign planning and set-up. The on-site installation and configuration of the detector was supported by the project’s external expert Scott Chambers. Due to the failure of a component, the detector’s resistor cascade had to be replaced on 25 August 2025, after which, further necessary tests were conducted. Consequently, operational measurements commenced on 9 September 2025. The first check of the instrumental background count was performed on 12 September 2025. The first calibration was performed on 15 September 2025. The detector is set-up to automatically run a calibration every month, and an instrumental background check every 3 months.

This deliverable, D1.2, describes the quality control procedures established to ensure the regular and systematic quality control of the atmospheric radon measurements.

2. Atmospheric radon measurements

The NuClim atmospheric radon monitor uses a Campbell Scientific CR300 data logger to store raw radon counts, along with output from a range of operational and diagnostic sensors. Measurements are performed at 10-second intervals and subsequently aggregated (averaged or summed) to 30-minute intervals. The Radon Detector Monitor software operating on the controlling computer saves all data (and operational system messages) to monthly SQLite database files (*.db) and stores a copy of the 30-minute totals and averages in monthly ASCII files (*.csv). Monthly datafiles of raw measurements (both database and text files) are preserved in the project’s NextCloud shared area, under Data.

The datafiles are structured in tabular format with the following fields:

- **Year** Year of measurement
- **DOY** Julian day of year
- **Month** Month of year
- **DOM** Day of month
- **Time** Time (hh:mm UTC)
- **ExFlow** Sampling flow rate (external flow loop) LPM
- **GM** Uncalibrated flow rate
- **InFlow** Air velocity (m/s) (internal flow loop)
- **HV** High voltage supplied to the detector head (V)
- **Spare** Unused (Legacy channel from prior software version)
- **LLD** Raw radon counts (all counts from PMT > 0.5 V)
- **ULD** Noise counts (all counts from PMT > 1.0 V)
- **TankP** Uncalibrated differential pressure signal
- **Temp** Temperature (C) of the logger wiring panel
- **AirT** Air temperature (C) inside the radon detector
- **RelHum** Relative humidity (%) inside the radon detector
- **Press** Absolute air pressure (hPa) inside the radon detector
- **Batt** Supply voltage to the data logger (V)
- **Comments** Unused (Legacy channel from prior software version)
- **Flag** Integer system status flag (0 normal; 1 background; 2 calibration; 4 maintenance)
- **TankPPa** Differential pressure (Pa) between inside of the detector and ambient
- **BV_Temp** Temperature recorded by pressure sensor (C)
- **BV_Qual_Min** Pressure sensor data quality indicator
- **ApproxRadon** Approximate radon concentration (based on assumed background and calibration)

On a daily to weekly basis, it is advisable to confirm that the basic operational parameters are within a sensible range. The sampling flow rate should be between $80 \text{ L} \cdot (60 \text{ s})^{-1}$ - $90 \text{ L} \cdot (60 \text{ s})^{-1}$, the internal flow velocity should be between 11 m s^{-1} - 12 m s^{-1} , the voltage supplied to the detector head should be between 770 V - 780 V, the differential pressure should be between 150 Pa - 250 Pa, and the noise counts should be mostly zero (occasional deviations allowed).

The air temperature, pressure and relative humidity time series are not required for detector operation or diagnostics, but they are useful in post processing to perform “standard temperature/pressure” corrections of the radon concentration, and dry air mole fraction corrections (required when comparing observed and simulated radon data).

3. Data preprocessing

The data files of atmospheric radon measurements are regularly preprocessed (at least once per week), as illustrated for September 2025 in the Jupyter notebook presented in the Appendix.

The first step involves checking the continuity of the data and returning the number of gaps identified in the dataset. If gaps are present, a full join is performed to align the time sequence in the datafile with a complete reference sequence, resulting in a preprocessed dataset with all expected timestamps and the flag NA marking missing values. The R code used for this is presented in Figure 1.

```
## function to print the number of gaps
count.gaps = function(posixdates) {

  gaps=length(which(c(1,round(diff(unclass(posixdates)/(60*30)))) != 1))
  print(paste("number of gaps =",gaps))
  return(gaps)
}

## Function create a continuous time series
fill.gaps = function(data) {

  start.time = data$DateTime[1]
  end.time = data$DateTime[length(data$DateTime)]

  all.times = seq.POSIXt(start.time, to=end.time, by = 60*30)

  df = data.frame(DateTime = all.times, stringsAsFactors = FALSE)
  data.all.times = full_join(df, data)

  return(data.all.times)
}
```

Figure 1: R code for checking and ensuring temporal continuity.

The next preprocessing step involves selecting the measurements corresponding to normal operation, as well as those associated with instrumental background and calibration activities. This selection is performed using the corresponding flag. The resulting data subsets are then stored separately, and quality control procedures (described in the next section) are applied to each subset.

4. Data quality control

Time series plots

The atmospheric radon data are first inspected using monthly plots of the following parameters: external flow, internal flow, voltage, differential pressure, radon counts, noise counts, air temperature, and relative humidity. These plots are generated automatically for each data subset (normal, calibration, and background) using the function `plot.radon.meas` (Figure 2).

Quality control of background and calibration measurements

For the calibration and background data, the quality control flag is manually set based on inspection of the plots. The default value of 0 indicates that the data have passed the quality control assessment, while a value of 9 denotes a suspect measurement.

The quality-controlled datafiles of calibration and background measurements for individual months are named *data_calibration_YYYY_mm.txt* and *data_background_YYYY_mm.txt*, respectively, where *YYYY* denotes the year and *mm* the month. The files are structured in space-separated tabular format with the following fields:

- Year Year in YYYY format
- DOY Julian day of year
- Month Month of year
- DOM Day of month
- Time Time (hh:mm UTC)
- ExFlow External flow (L/min)
- GM Uncalibrated flow rate
- InFlow Internal flow (m/s)
- HV Voltage (V)
- LLD Radon counts
- ULD Noise counts
- TankP Differential pressure (Pa)
- Temp Temperature of the logger wiring panel (°C)
- AirT Air temperature inside the radon detector (°C)
- RelHum Relative humidity inside the radon detector (%)
- Press Absolute air pressure inside the radon detector (hPa)
- Batt Supply voltage to the data logger (V)
- TankPPa Differential pressure between inside of the detector and ambient (Pa)
- BV_Temp Temperature recorded by pressure sensor (°C)
- BV_Qual_Min Pressure sensor data quality indicator
- ApproxRadon Approximate radon concentration
- QC_flag_manual Non-automatic QC flag (0 or 9)

```
## Function to plot radon detector measurements
plot.all.variables = function(data, colorvalue) {

  exflow = data |> ggplot(aes(DateTime, ExFlow)) +
    geom_line(color = colorvalue) +
    geom_point(color = colorvalue) +
    # geom_hline(yintercept = 80, color = "darkgreen") +
    # geom_hline(yintercept = 90, color = "darkgreen") +
    labs(x = "Time", y = "L/min", title = "External flow")

  inflow = data |> ggplot(aes(DateTime, InFlow)) +
    geom_line(color = colorvalue) +
    geom_point(color = colorvalue) +
    # geom_hline(yintercept = 11, color = "darkgreen") +
    # geom_hline(yintercept = 12, color = "darkgreen") +
    labs(x = "Time", y = "L/min", title = "Internal flow")

  voltage = data |> ggplot(aes(DateTime, HV)) +
    geom_line(color = colorvalue) +
    geom_point(color = colorvalue) +
    # geom_hline(yintercept = 770, color = "darkgreen") +
    # geom_hline(yintercept = 780, color = "darkgreen") +
    labs(x = "Time", y = "V", title = "Voltage")

  tankpressure = data |> ggplot(aes(DateTime, TankPPa)) +
    geom_line(color = colorvalue) +
    geom_point(color = colorvalue) +
    # geom_hline(yintercept = 150, color = "darkgreen") +
    # geom_hline(yintercept = 250, color = "darkgreen") +
    labs(x = "Time", y = "Pa", title = "Differential pressure")

  radoncounts = data |> ggplot(aes(DateTime, LLD)) +
    geom_line(color = colorvalue) +
    geom_point(color = colorvalue) +
    labs(x = "Time", y = "counts", title = "Radon counts")

  noisecounts = data |> ggplot(aes(DateTime, ULD)) +
    geom_line(color = colorvalue) +
    geom_point(color = colorvalue) +
    labs(x = "Time", y = "counts", title = "Noise counts")

  airt = data |> ggplot(aes(DateTime, AirT)) +
    geom_line(color = colorvalue) +
    geom_point(color = colorvalue) +
    labs(x = "Time", y = "°C", title = "Air T")

  relhum = data |> ggplot(aes(DateTime, RelHum)) +
    geom_line(color = colorvalue) +
    geom_point(color = colorvalue) +
    labs(x = "Time", y = "%", title = "Relative humidity")

  plot_grid(exflow, inflow, voltage, tankpressure, radoncounts, noisecounts,
            airt, relhum, ncol = 2, align = "v")
}
```

Figure 2: R code for automatic plotting of atmospheric radon measurements.

Quality control of normal measurements

For normal measurements quality control flags are generated automatically according to the specifications detailed in Table 1. The corresponding R code is shown in Figure 3. After the automatic assignment of flags, an additional flag (value = 9) can be manually set by the user performing the quality control, based on a subjective assessment of potentially suspect data identified from the time series plots. A quality control flag value of 0 indicates that the data have passed the corresponding quality control test.

```
## Function to flag radon detector measurements
```

```
flag.radon.meas=function(data.meas){  
  
  n=dim(data.meas)[1]  
  
  qc.flag.exflow=rep(0,n)  
  exflow.min=80  
  exflow.max=90  
  qc.flag.exflow[which(data.meas$exflow < exflow.min)]=1  
  qc.flag.exflow[which(data.meas$exflow > exflow.max)]=2  
  
  qc.flag.inflow=rep(0,n)  
  inflow.min=11  
  inflow.max=12  
  qc.flag.inflow[which(data.meas$inflow < inflow.min)]=3  
  qc.flag.inflow[which(data.meas$inflow > inflow.max)]=4  
  
  qc.flag.hv=rep(0,n)  
  hv.min=770  
  hv.max=780  
  qc.flag.hv[which(data.meas$hv < hv.min)]=5  
  qc.flag.hv[which(data.meas$hv > hv.max)]=6  
  
  qc.flag.tankPa=rep(0,n)  
  tankPa.min=150  
  tankPa.max=250  
  qc.flag.tankPa[which(data.meas$tankPa < tankPa.min)]=7  
  qc.flag.tankPa[which(data.meas$tankPa > tankPa.max)]=8  
  
  qc.flag=cbind(qc.flag.exflow,qc.flag.inflow, qc.flag.hv, qc.flag.tankPa)  
  
  return (data.frame(qc.flag))  
  
}
```

Figure 3: R code for automatic input of QC flags to normal radon measurements.

Table 1: Table of QC flags applied to the atmospheric radon measurements.

QC flag	Description
1	External flow < 80 L·(60 s) ⁻¹
2	External flow > 90 L·(60 s) ⁻¹
3	Internal flow < 11 L·(60 s) ⁻¹
4	Internal flow > 12 L·(60 s) ⁻¹
5	Voltage < 770 V
6	Voltage > 780 V
7	Differential pressure < 150 Pa
8	Differential pressure > 250 Pa
9	Manual flag – suspect measurement (from plot inspection)

The quality-controlled datafiles of normal radon measurements for individual months are named *data_normal_YYYY_mm.txt*, where *YYYY* denotes the year and *mm* the month. The files are structured in space-separated tabular format with the following fields:

- Year Year in YYYY format
- DOY Julian day of year
- Month Month of year
- DOM Day of month
- Time Time (hh:mm UTC)
- ExFlow External flow (L/min)
- GM Uncalibrated flow rate
- InFlow Internal flow (m/s)
- HV Voltage (V)
- LLD Radon counts
- ULD Noise counts
- TankP Differential pressure (Pa)
- Temp Temperature of the logger wiring panel (°C)
- AirT Air temperature inside the radon detector (°C)
- RelHum Relative humidity inside the radon detector (%)
- Press Absolute air pressure inside the radon detector (hPa)
- Batt Supply voltage to the data logger (V)
- TankPPa Differential pressure between inside of the detector and ambient (Pa)
- BV_Temp Temperature recorded by pressure sensor (°C)
- BV_Qual_Min Pressure sensor data quality indicator
- ApproxRadon Approximate radon concentration
- QC_flag_exflow Automatic QC flag for external flow (1 or 2)
- QC_flag_inflow Automatic QC flag for internal flow (3 or 4)
- QC_flag_hv Automatic QC flag for voltage (5 or 6)
- QC_flag_tankPa Automatic QC flag for differential pressure (7 or 8)
- QC_flag_manual Non-automatic QC flag (0 or 9)

5. Data quality assurance

The atmospheric radon measurements are inspected regularly (at least weekly) for application of the quality control procedures described in the previous section. Calibration measurements are performed automatically every month, and an instrumental background check every 3 months.

Calibration

A calibration event constitutes introducing a steady stream of known radon concentration into the radon detector's sampling line for a period of 5 h to 6 h, then stopping this injection. Radon-free compressed instrument air is used to flush a well-characterised source (8.51 kBq of ^{226}Ra ; designed, built and tested by the Czech Metrology Institute) at a rate of $0.2 \text{ L} \cdot (60 \text{ s})^{-1}$ into the detector's $\sim 85 \text{ L} \cdot (60 \text{ s})^{-1}$ sampling flow. Prior to starting the injection, the source is flushed to the open air for 8 hours. After the injection is completed, air inside the detector takes 5 h – 6 h to return to reporting ambient radon concentrations reliably. A typical calibration event is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Example calibration event for the 1500L radon detector.

The calibration process for an ANSTO two-filter dual flow-loop radon monitor is detailed in Chambers et al. (2022), and Kikaj et al., (2025). Briefly though, to process a calibration peak, the first step is to approximate the ambient outdoor radon concentration during the calibration event by linearly interpolating the radon count rate between the beginning and end of the calibration event (indicated by the dashed red line in Figure 4). This is equivalent to assuming a gradual/linear change in ambient radon concentrations over the 10 h - 12 h period of the calibration injection. The fact that, in reality, this is often not the case, this assumption constitutes the largest potential source of error in the whole calibration process. For remote oceanic sites, this assumption is usually satisfied under most conditions. For conditions under which this assumption is not satisfied, the larger the source used to calibrate the detector, the smaller the associated error in making this assumption. This source of uncertainty is why it is recommended to calibrate the detector once a month (rather than just twice a year). This way, any calibration events for which this assumption is not met can be excluded.

The second step is to estimate the “net peak counts per second” of the calibration event (see Figure 4) by subtracting the ambient count value at the time of peak raw radon counts from the peak NetCount value and dividing by 1800 s (for 30-minute measurements).

The third step is to estimate the expected radon concentration inside the detector at equilibrium based on the source strength and the detector's sampling flow rate. Taking the ratio of the source's radon delivery rate ($\text{Bq} \cdot (60 \text{ s})^{-1}$ of ^{222}Rn) and detector's sampling rate ($\text{L} \cdot (60 \text{ s})^{-1}$) and scaling by 1000 to convert from L to m^3 , yields an equilibrium radon concentration inside the detector of approximately 12 Bq m^{-3} .

The detector's calibration factor ($\text{s} \cdot \text{Bq} \cdot \text{m}^{-3})^{-1}$) is then derived by scaling the ratio of the net peak counts per second and the radon concentration by a small factor (~ 1.01), to account for the fact that after 6 h of injection, the concentration of radon within the detector will not quite have fully reached equilibrium. This scale factor will depend on the length of the injection time, and the detector's sampling flow rate. The model used to derive this scale factor is described in Griffiths et al., (2016).

Instrumental background

A background check is approximated by stopping all flow (internal and external flow) of the detector for a period of 24 hours. After 5 h - 6 h, all short-lived radon progeny on the detector head's second filter have decayed, and an average background count over the last 18 hours can be determined. A typical background event is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Typical detector response over a 24-hour period after disconnecting power to the internal and external flow loop blowers. The quarterly instrumental background is usually determined as the median 30-minute count rate over the last 18 hours.

As demonstrated by Röttger et al., (2023), this approximate instrumental background approach is not able to account for the self-generation (ingrowth) of radon within the detector by trace ^{226}Ra contamination of building materials. However, this effect is not typically large, and – since the half-life of ^{226}Ra is 1600 y – the ingrowth of radon is expected to be quite consistent over the lifetime of an instrument. Consequently, at most this approximation would result in a measurement offset of a few 10s of milli-becquerels, or less.

Calculation of radon concentration

Half-hourly radon concentrations as calculated as

$$[Rn, Bq m^{-3}] = \frac{(NetCount - Background)}{30 \times 60 \times Calibration}$$

where NetCount is the difference between raw radon counts and noise counts, and Background and Calibration, are the half-hourly background and calibration values estimated from the analysis of calibration and background events.

Measurements from the ANSTO two-filter dual flow-loop radon detector result from gross alpha counting of ^{218}Po and ^{214}Po decay (see Figure 3 of Griffiths et al., (2016)). Consequently, around 40 % of the signal of a change in radon concentration arrives more than an hour after a radon pulse is delivered (i.e. the instruments have a response time of around 45 minutes to half-peak magnitude). Because of the slow instrument response, the radon concentrations derived using only the background and calibration procedures described above, exhibit a “smoothed” appearance, and amplitudes of rapid changes in radon concentration are typically reduced. To eliminate this problem, Griffiths et al., (2016) derived a deconvolution routine to correct for the instrument’s response time (also available on Github: <https://github.com/anstoradonlab/rdfix>).

As demonstrated in Figure 6, the response time corrected radon concentrations much more closely represent physical changes occurring in the atmosphere as observed by more rapidly responding instruments. As indicated by the light grey shading around the black line in Figure 6, the deconvolution routine does add a small degree of uncertainty to the final result (which is much smaller than the error the routine corrects for).

Figure 6: Comparison of observed (blue) 30-minute radon concentrations and response-time corrected (black) 30-minute radon concentrations compared with 1-minute CO₂ observations.

References

Chambers, S. D., Griffiths, A. D., Williams, A. G., Sisoutham, O., Morosh, V., Röttger, S., Mertes, F., & Röttger, A. (2022). Portable two-filter dual-flow-loop ^{222}Rn detector: Stand-alone monitor and calibration transfer device. *Advances in Geosciences*, 57, 63-80, <https://doi.org/10.5194/adgeo-57-63-2022>.

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Röttger, S., Röttger, A., Mertes, F., Morosch, V., Ballé, T., Chambers, S. (2023). Evolution of traceable radon emanation sources from MBq to few Bq, *Applied radiation and isotopes*, 196, 110726, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apradiso.2023.110726>.

Appendix – Jupyter notebook

Appendix - notebook for preprocessing radon raw data

1 NuClim Radon measurements - 2025/09

First, we load packages and custom code

```
[1]: suppressPackageStartupMessages(library(dplyr))
      suppressPackageStartupMessages(library(ggplot2))
      suppressPackageStartupMessages(library(cowplot))

      source("codeRadonQC.R")

      options(warn=-1)
```

Define the theme for ggplot

```
[2]: set_theme(theme_classic())
```

Now, the data:

```
[3]: dat = read.csv(file = "AzoresSep25.CSV", header = TRUE)
```

We need to convert the date to an R date format:

```
[4]: dat = dat |> mutate(DateTime = as.POSIXct(paste(Year,
      "-", Month, "-", DOM, Time, sep = ""),
      format = "%Y-%m-%d %H:%M", tz = "UTC"))
```

Now, we can check whether there are any gaps in the data. For this, we convert the date to seconds (`unclass`, specifically it shows seconds since 1 January 1970) and then divide by 1800 (because a measurement is made every 30 minutes and there are 60 seconds in each minute). Thus, we get half hours consecutively numbered and calculate the difference between each data point in the next (`diff`). This difference is then rounded to the next integer (`round`) and if it is not 1 it is added to a vector. From this vector, the length is determined and it represents the number of gaps.

In case of gaps, these are filled by comparing timestamps to a regular 30-minute sequence, followed by a full join, producing a complete set of timestamps with missing values encoded as NA.

```
[5]: gaps=count.gaps(dat$DateTime)

      if (gaps != 0) {dat=fill.gaps(dat)}
```

```
[1] "number of gaps = 0"
```

1.1 Background measurements

Background measurements are flagged with 1, so we filter the complete dataset for only the background measurement data.

```
[6]: data.background = dat |> filter(Flag == 1)
      gaps=count.gaps(data.background$DateTime)

      if (gaps != 0) {data.background=fill.gaps(data.background)}
```

```
[1] "number of gaps = 0"
```

Now we plot the different parameters for the background measurements.

```
[7]: plot.all.variables(data.background, "darkmagenta")
```


Add manual QC flag (change from default 0 value to a value of 9) if a measurement is suspect (from inspection of the plots)

```
[8]: qc.background.manual = data.frame(qc.manual=rep(0,dim(data.background)[1]))

data.background <- data.background |> mutate(
  QC_flag_manual = qc.background.manual$qc.manual)
```

And export the data

```
[9]: # remove unused columns
data.background = data.background %>% select(-Flag, -DateTime, -Spare, -Comments)

write.table(file = "data_background_2025_09.txt",
            data.background,
            quote = FALSE, row.names = FALSE)
```

1.2 Calibration measurements

This works exactly like for the background measurements, just with a flag 2.

```
[10]: data.calibration = dat |> filter(Flag == 2)
count.gaps(data.calibration$DateTime)
```

```
[1] "number of gaps = 0"
```

```
0
```

```
[11]: plot.all.variables(data.calibration, "darkorange")
```


Apply QC flags to calibration measurements

```
[12]: qc.calibration.manual = data.frame(qc.manual=rep(0,dim(data.calibration)[1]))
data.calibration <- data.calibration |> mutate(
  QC_flag_manual = qc.calibration.manual$qc.manual)
```

Export calibration measurements

```
[13]: # remove unused columns
data.calibration = data.calibration %>% select(-Flag, -DateTime, -Spare,
  ↪-Comments)
write.table(file = "data_calibration_2025_09.txt", data.calibration,
```

```
quote = FALSE, row.names = FALSE)
```

1.3 Normal measurements

Now we come to the normal measurements (neither background nor calibration measurements). We remove any data that has not the flag 0 (bad data, background measurements, calibration measurements, ...).

```
[14]: data.normal = dat |> mutate(across(!c(DateTime, Flag),
~ case_when(Flag != 0 ~ NA,
.default = .)))
```

And now, the obligatory plots.

```
[15]: plot.all.variables(data.normal, "darkblue")
```


Apply QC flags to normal measurements

```
[16]: qc.normal=flag.radon.meas(data.normal)
qc.normal.manual = data.frame(qc.manual=rep(0,dim(data.normal)[1]))

data.normal <- data.normal |> mutate(
  QC_flag_exflow = qc.normal$qc.flag.exflow,
  QC_flag_inflow = qc.normal$qc.flag.inflow,
  QC_flag_hv = qc.normal$qc.flag.hv,
  QC_flag_tankPa = qc.normal$qc.flag.tankPa,
  QC_flag_manual = qc.normal.manual$qc.manual
)
```

And the export :)

```
[17]: # remove unused columns
data.normal.out = data.normal %>% select(-Flag, -DateTime, -Spare, -Comments)

write.table(file = "data_normal_2025_09.txt", data.normal.out, quote = FALSE,
            row.names = FALSE)
```

And a plot of just the radon counts over time.

```
[18]: options(repr.plot.width=10, repr.plot.height=4)

data.normal |> ggplot(aes(DateTime, LLD)) + geom_line() + geom_point() +
  labs(x = "Time", y = "counts", title = "Radon counts")
```



```
[ ]:
```